

PEDAGOGICAL IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS APPLICATION OF TECHNOLOGIES

Sanayev Ikram Iskandar

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the Department of Physical Culture.

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Abstract. *The purpose of the article is that every pedagogue who teaches should research more about himself and teach using the methods that are widely promoted nowadays. The pedagogue is always interactive in the process of education. if he can use the methods correctly and effectively, he can interest students in the lesson and increase the quality of the lesson.*

Keys words: *interactive, education, pedagogue, continuity, pedagogical technologies, survey, survey, competition, method, educator, researcher.*

A teacher, including a coach, unlike other professions, is required to be in search throughout his life. Otherwise, it will fall behind the times. Even when he is sought, only if he does not stop with simple research, but with serious and creative research, he is constantly and constantly engaged in it, which creates the basis for him not to be behind the times.

We all know that the content, goals and tasks, forms and methods of the educational process are improving, and the occurrence of such changes in our society requires the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. It is necessary to use the most advanced pedagogical technologies in order to increase the effectiveness of population education in order for our society to take a place among the developed countries in the global community.

I believe that the physical education, physical development, health, physical fitness of the students of the higher educational institution, as well as the transition to new modern educational technology, will have an undoubted effect on raising a well-rounded person.

The concept of educational technology is a science (or teaching) that provides information on the organization of the educational (teaching) process at a high level of skill and art. means name. Pedagogical technology is a means by which a teacher (educator) influences students (students) in certain conditions with the help of teaching (educational) tools, and otherwise, as a product of influence, guarantees the rapid formation of predetermined personality qualities in them. is a process.

The activity of the teacher based on pedagogical technologies is considered as a creative process and a result of creative activity.

A change in the pattern of communication between a teacher and a student is one of the conditions of pedagogical technology.

Purpose: to organize the cognitive activity of higher education students in pre-school and primary education on the subjects of sports science with the help of selected teaching methods and increase their mastery.

Task:

> Organization of interactive games for educational processes in accordance with educational requirements and content.

> We, the teachers, in the course of the lesson, first of all, provide the students with deep and solid knowledge of subjects, and we intend to educate them to be interested in knowledge and to work hard.

> One of the main requirements for the training is to improve the effectiveness of interactive methods and methods.

Therefore, the teacher appears as the author, developer, researcher, user and promoter of new pedagogical technologies, theories, concepts.

The central problem of pedagogical technology is to ensure the achievement of the educational goal through the development of the student's personality.

The content of the educational process is the effectiveness of the level of knowledge that the teacher imparts to the student. Therefore, it is necessary for a teacher to teach using new methods, based on a deep understanding of the essence of the new pedagogical technology.

The form, method and means of training lead to ensuring the success of the educational process.

Research method:

- interactive games;
- questionnaire;
- test questions;

Below we will consider some of the projects implemented through pedagogical technology to improve the knowledge of III-level students in classes.

The course of the lesson:

The teacher prepares the room for working with groups before the lesson. In the room where students enter, there are places for 2 groups, and these places are marked with numbers.

Students take the cards from the teacher's table with no visible numbers and sit in the place designated for the group with that number. All students are divided into groups in this way. Depending on the number of students, the number and order of groups may change. Then the lecture text to be passed is distributed to the groups. The text of the lecture will be divided into 4 parts. Each handout will be numbered. After the groups have mastered the texts assigned to them, the groups will be re-formed according to the sequence numbers given on the handout and will have to explain the material they have mastered to their partners. After this process, students return to their old groups.

Now the teacher asks the groups questions about the topic. Whichever spirit responds best is judged accordingly. In this game, students acquire both mastery and explanation skills.

Conclusion In order to check how effective these methods were, we compared the learning rates of the group that was taught on the basis of pedagogical technologies and the groups that were taught in the traditional way. For this, each group was given 10 test questions on the topic covered at the end of the lesson. The results of the research showed that the level of mastery of the group taught on the basis of pedagogical technologies was higher than the other group. We observed that students' interest in the lesson has increased significantly.

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